

Dependent Weighted Aggregation Operators of Hesitant Fuzzy Numbers

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Abstract : In this paper, motivated by the ideas of dependent weighted aggregation operators, we develop some new hesitant fuzzy dependent weighted aggregation operators to aggregate the input arguments taking the form of hesitant fuzzy numbers rather than exact numbers, or intervals. In fact, we propose three hesitant fuzzy dependent weighted averaging(HFDWA) operators, and three hesitant fuzzy dependent weighted geometric(HFDWG) operators based on different weight vectors, and the most prominent characteristic of these operators is that the associated weights only depend on the aggregated hesitant fuzzy numbers and can relieve the influence of unfair hesitant fuzzy numbers on the aggregated results by assigning low weights to those “false” and “biased” ones. Some examples are given to illustrate the efficiency of the proposed operators.

Keywords : Hesitant fuzzy numbers, hesitant fuzzy dependent weighted averaging(HFDWA) operators, hesitant fuzzy dependent weighted geometric(HFDWG) operators.

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